

IDENTIFICATION OF ELASTIC MODULI OF A THIN ORTHOTROPIC PLATE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, unknown material constants of a thin orthotropic plate are identified by using a hybrid procedure consisting of numerical and experimental parts: The bending problem of a cantilevered thin homogeneous orthotropic plate is solved by using finite elements to obtain equations that contain deformation data, loading and orthotropic elastic moduli. Then, the bending deformation of the plate is measured experimentally. Experimental measurements and equations obtained from finite element solution are combined in the inverse method to determine the unknown elastic moduli. The results are compared to results obtained from standard mechanical tests.

INTRODUCTION

In general, unknown material properties are determined by independent standard mechanical tests. But, each of these tests requires expensive testing apparatus and specimen preparation procedures. In some cases, it is not even possible to prepare appropriate specimens because the dimensions of the material available are not suitable to be used as standard test specimens. There is always a need for more efficient and fast material property identification procedures.

A two dimensional homogeneous orthotropic plate has two elastic moduli along the first and second directions, E_x , and E_y , Poisson's ratios ν_{xy} and ν_{yx} , and shear modulus G_{xy} .

In this study, a hybrid method that combines numerical and experimental results is used to determine the two-dimensional orthotropic elastic moduli. The deflections of the plate are experimentally measured. They are used in finite elements equations where the elastic moduli are unknown. Resulting equations are solved for unknown elastic moduli.

There are various studies in literature that determine the mechanical properties of orthotropic materials. Kernevez *et al.* [1] developed an experimental procedure to obtain the orthotropic plate bending rigidities of a thin plate. They used finite differences method to solve the classical orthotropic thin plate bending equation. They simulated experiments numerically for bending under several loading configurations. By giving initial bending rigidities, they tried to reach the exact deflection values by changing the bending rigidities using a minimization method. Pierron and Grédiac [2] proposed a single test to identify all of the four in-plane stiffness components of an orthotropic material instead of several independent standard tests. They applied tension and bending loads to their T - shaped test specimens. Grédiac and Vautrin [3, 4] and Grediac [5, 6] determined the bending rigidities of a thin anisotropic plate by doing bending tests on a plate specimen. They derived the bending rigidities from the relations between the bending rigidities, applied loads and plate curvature.

In inverse methods, numerical and experimental techniques are combined to extend the capability of the analytical relations to more complicated domains [7, 8, 9]. The inverse technique requires an error analysis and its minimization for both experimental and numerical methods and the ways to minimize these errors. Beck and Woodbury [10] gave an overview of the inverse analysis techniques to get more accurate results. In inverse analysis, one should know how to extract the desired output from redundant experimental data. Grédiac [11] and Constantinescu [12] have studied how to process experimental data obtained from plate bending tests to determine the most accurate plate bending rigidity values.

In this paper, the bending problem of a point loaded rectangular orthotropic thin plate is described and a numerical solution is presented. Following the numerical solution, the procedure used to measure the deflections is explained. Then, the *inverse analysis* where numerical analyses and experimental measurements are combined to identify the unknown elastic moduli is outlined. The validity of the proposed method is tested through numerical simulations, and results are compared to those of standard tensile tests.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A thin orthotropic homogeneous material has five material constants: E_x , E_y , ν_{xy} , ν_{yx} , G_{xy} of which four are independent, ($\nu_{xy}/\nu_{yx} = E_x/E_y$). The constitutive relations for a thin homogeneous orthotropic plate are as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_x & -\nu_{yx}/E_y & 0 \\ -\nu_{xy}/E_x & 1/E_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

EMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDThe equation governing the bending of a two dimensional homogeneous orthotropic plate is defined as,

$$D_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} = p, \quad (2)$$

where w is the displacement normal to the plate surface and p is the distributed load on the plate. D_{11} , D_{12} , D_{22} and D_{66} are called the *bending rigidities* of the plate and are outlined below:

$$D_{11} = \frac{1}{12} \frac{E_x^2 t^3}{(E_x - E_y \nu_{xy}^2)}, \quad D_{12} = \frac{1}{12} \frac{E_x E_y \nu_{xy} t^3}{(E_x - E_y \nu_{xy}^2)}, \quad D_{22} = \frac{1}{12} \frac{E_x E_y t^3}{(E_x - E_y \nu_{xy}^2)}, \quad D_{66} = \frac{G_{xy} t^3}{12}. \quad (3)$$

EMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDIn this problem, the Poisson's ratio, ν_{xy} is assumed to be known.EMBED The goal is to determine E_x , E_y , G_{xy} , through three bending rigidities D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{66} . EMBEDEMBEDEMBEDFor numerical and experimental calculations, a 250 × 250 mm cantilevered thin plate, 1.51 mm thick, is used as shown in Fig. 1. The $y=0$ edge is fully clamped. To develop the inverse identification procedure using finite elements solution, the plate is divided into 25 × 25 four-node elements and a 12-term polynomial approximation function is used.

$$w(x,y) = a_1 + a_2 x + a_3 y + a_4 x y + a_5 x^2 + a_6 y^2 + a_7 x^2 y + a_8 x y^2$$

$$+ a_9 x^3 + a_{10} y^3 + a_{11} x^3 y + a_{12} x y^3. \quad (4)$$

Fig 1 Cantilevered thin plate

Loads P_i 's are applied at several locations over 10 x 10 mm element surfaces uniformly. To test the validity of the assumptions made in Eq's. (1-2) and the results of the finite elements formulation used here, calculated deflections are compared to those of MSC MARC for distributed and point loading cases. In MSC MARC, three point loading cases are solved by using four node bilinear thin shell element (element number 139), four node bilinear thick shell element (element number 75), eighth node quadratic thick shell element (element number 22) and eighth node bilinear constrained thin shell element (element number 72). The results showed that there is almost no difference. Eq's. (1-2) and higher order theories yield similar deflection results. Increasing the number of elements does not change the deflection magnitudes, as a result, the discretization used here is assumed to be sufficient for the stated problem.

Another check is done to test the linear deformation assumption that Eq. (2) is based on. The displacements calculated by MSC MARC by using linear and non-linear assumptions are compared. For point load that causes a deflection of 10 mm at the edge $y=250$ mm, there is a ± 2 percent difference between the linear and nonlinear solutions. Therefore the errors that come from the linear deformation assumption made in Eq. (2) is negligible for the stated problem. The set of finite elements equations obtained from 25×25 elements contains $26 \times 26 \times 3 = 2028$ equations. For the unknown primary variables, these equations can be reduced to $26 \times 25 \times 3 = 1950$ equations because the values on the clamped edge are known. These 1950 equations can be expressed as follows:

$$[K(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{66})]_{1950 \times 1950} \{w\}_{1950} = \{f\}_{1950} \quad (5)$$

An objective function g is defined as the sum of the squares of differences between the experimentally measured displacements and the displacements found by using the iterated elastic moduli.

$$g = \sum_{i=1}^n (w_{measured} - w_{iterated})^2, \quad (6)$$

where $w_{iterated}$ is the displacement calculated using the finite element solution and the iterated elastic moduli; n is the number of nodes where displacements are measured. The elastic moduli minimizing the objective function are the unknown elastic moduli that are sought.

For the isotropic case, the three bending rigidities can be written in terms of the elastic modulus, E , the Poisson's ratio, ν , and the thickness, t . Therefore for the isotropic case Eq. (5) can be written as:

$$[K(E, \nu, t)]_{1950 \times 1950} \{w\}_{1950} = \{f\}_{1950}. \quad (7)$$

Substituting the values v and t , K will contain only E , as the unknown variable. E can be factored out, and the inverse can be evaluated as follows:

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$$\{w\}_{1950} = \frac{1}{E} [K]^{-1}_{1950 \times 1950} \{f\}_{1950}. \quad (8)$$

The objective function g in Eq. (6) will therefore take the following form:

$$g(E) = \sum_{i=1}^n (w_{measured} - w(E))^2. \quad (9)$$

By using a minimization method, the value of E that minimizes the objective function $g(E)$ can easily be found as the material property to be determined.

In the orthotropic case, the K in Eq. (5) contains three variables D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{66} . It is not easy to find the inverse of K in closed form, and write an objective function explicitly in terms of bending rigidities as done in the isotropic case. As a result, to minimize the objective function the conjugate gradient method [13] is followed. The objective function to be minimized is:

$$g(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{66}) = \sum_{i=1}^n (w_{measured} - w(D_{11}, D_{22}, D_{66}))^2. \quad (10)$$

The algorithm of the minimization procedure is given below:

- Iteration begins by giving starting values for D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{66} EMBED.
- The objective function is evaluated in terms of D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{66} using measured displacements and the finite elements results EMBEDEM EMBED.
- Conjugate gradient method is used to minimize the objective function.
- The three bending rigidities for the next iteration are calculated by the conjugate gradient method using a step size that decreases as the iteration index increases.
- The objective function is recalculated using new bending rigidities. The value of the objective function gives us an understanding of how much the difference between the iterated displacement values and the measurements is. The iteration stops when the objective function is below a certain value.

A numerical check is done for a 250 x 250 mm plate with 1.51 mm thickness. The plate is discretized using 10 x 10 finite elements. A load of 20.67 N is applied uniformly on the element face at the right bottom corner ($x=0$, $y=250$ mm). The minimization procedure explained above is used to identify the three unknown bending rigidities, D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{66} and the corresponding elastic moduli E_x , E_y , G_{xy} . The Poisson's ratio ν_{xy} is taken to be 0.285. In Table 1, the convergence of the minimization is given. Instead of experimentally measured displacements, displacements calculated by finite elements for given elastic moduli are used. At the 27th iteration, D_{22} and D_{66} converge to the exact values, but D_{11} diverges. Once D_{22} and D_{66} reach the exact values, D_{11} starts to converge to the exact value as well. At the 325th iteration, the values obtained for the iterated bending rigidities are quite satisfactory. To have an idea on the effectiveness of the proposed method, the problem stated above is solved for known elastic moduli (Table 2, first row). The calculated displacements are used as $w_{measured}$ in Eq. (5) so that calculated elastic moduli converge to those in the first row used in

calculations. The calculated elastic moduli are shown in the second row of Table 2. To account for the effect of experimental errors, the displacements are perturbed by certain amounts.

Table 1 Convergence of the minimization procedure

Iteration #	D_{11} [Nm]	D_{22} [Nm]	D_{66} [Nm]	Obj.Func.
1	85.000	50.000	15.000	1.3691E-03
10	87.260	56.764	17.464	3.6905E-05
20	90.023	63.849	21.130	2.2692E-06
27	90.650	65.920	25.590	1.4097E-07
40	89.180	66.454	24.902	4.0129E-04
80	82.592	64.766	25.239	7.9300E-08
120	79.432	65.217	25.266	3.0105E-09
150	77.556	65.376	25.455	1.9784E-09
180	75.965	65.269	25.341	1.3088E-09
203	75.568	65.333	25.332	1.7955E-11
312	74.898	65.347	25.332	9.2124E-13
325	74.889	65.346	25.334	9.9824E-14

Table 2 Bending rigidities and elastic moduli found for different added perturbations to displacements

Added pert.	D_{11} [Nm]	D_{22} [Nm]	D_{66} [Nm]	E_x [GPa]	E_y [GPa]	G [GPa]	Obj.Fnc. [mm ²]	Ave.D iff. [mm]
Given	74.83	65.35	25.33	242.30	211.60	88.30	0.000E+00	0.000E+00
No pert.	74.89	65.35	25.33	242.52	211.61	88.30	9.982E-08	3.012E-05
0.001 mm	74.91	65.34	25.34	242.58	211.61	88.31	1.104E-04	1.002E-03
0.01 mm	75.36	65.34	25.33	244.17	211.70	88.30	1.100E-02	1.000E-02
0.05 mm	77.46	65.33	25.33	251.47	212.11	88.29	2.749E-01	4.999E-02
0.1 mm	80.23	65.31	25.33	261.12	212.61	88.28	1.100E+00	1.000E-01

The precision of the measurement device is added and subtracted subsequently from all of the 110 *measured* nodal displacements. The precisions of the measurement devices range from 0.001 mm to 0.1 mm as shown in Table 2. The bending rigidities and the corresponding elastic moduli found by using the perturbed solution vectors and the values of the objective functions at the end of the iterations are also given. To have an idea on the effectiveness of the proposed method, first, the problem stated above is solved. The initial values for the minimization procedure are $D_{11} = 85$ Nm, $D_{22} = 50$ Nm, $D_{66} = 15$ Nm that corresponds to $E_x = 282.10$ GPa, $E_y = 165.94$ GPa, $G_{xy} = 52.28$ GPa. Comparing the results given in Table 2, the elastic moduli found are still satisfactory for a measurement precision of 0.1 mm. This precision can be obtained from most measurement devices. The average difference of displacements per node on the right end column is calculated by dividing the objective function value by the total number of nodes and taking the square root of the quotient ($Average\ difference = (Objective\ function / n)^{1/2}$). It is seen that the average difference values are exactly the same values of added perturbations. This is expected because the perturbations are equally distributed.

In Table 3, the displacement values of the nodes on edge $y=250$ mm are given in mm for the exact elastic moduli and for the elastic moduli given in Table 2. It is seen that the values for 0.1 mm perturbation are very close to the exact values, although the D_{11} value did not converge to the exact one. This shows that changes in D_{11} do not affect the displacement values considerably.

It is seen that the change in deflection values when load distribution other than uniform are applied are much lower than the precision of the displacement measurement device for displacement ranges used. The maximum plate deflection under its own weight is calculated to be 0.89 mm. Since the plate is rolled, it is not perfectly flat. To account for these effects, the deflections of the nodes of interest are measured before loading. Then, unloaded plate deflections are subtracted from the loaded plate deflections so that the effects of the imperfections of the surface of the plate, and the weight of the plate can be eliminated.

Table 4 Elastic moduli in parallel and perpendicular drawing directions (Standard Tensile Test Results).

Number of specimen	Elastic Modulus [G Pa] in parallel direction	Elastic Modulus [G Pa] in perpendicular
1	249,7	210,5
2	234,8	223,2
3	253,6	212,1
4	235,2	215,5
5	250,2	208,1
6	230,1	187,7
Average	242,3	209,5
St. Dev.	9,1	10,9

Fig 2 Experimental setup

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Ten separate measurements are carried out as shown in Fig. 1 and as listed in Table 5. The coordinates and the magnitudes of loading, minimum and maximum nodal displacements at $y=250$ mm, and the total number of nodes where displacements are measured are tabulated in Table 5. Single load is applied in each experiment except in the third experiment where two loads are applied (Fig. 1).

Table 5 Loading and deformation summary of the 10 measurements

Exp. #	D_{11} [Nm]	D_{22} [Nm]	D_{66} [Nm]	E_x [GPa]	E_y [GPa]	G [GPa]	Obj. Fnc. [mm ²]	Ave. Diff. [mm]
1	73.92	64.08	18.52	239.5	207.6	64.6	0.511	0.059
2	76.46	64.11	3.26	248.3	208.2	11.3	0.599	0.065
3	77.28	66.32	24.25	250.6	215.0	84.5	1.554	0.093
4	77.74	64.10	30.29	252.8	208.5	105.6	0.290	0.043
5	76.07	63.60	24.08	247.1	206.6	83.9	0.208	0.037
6	82.08	63.38	17.81	268.2	207.1	62.1	0.368	0.049
7	84.99	62.36	17.61	278.6	204.4	61.4	0.401	0.051
8	80.72	64.37	27.83	263.1	209.8	97.0	0.170	0.033
9	68.02	62.55	18.54	219.4	201.7	64.6	0.541	0.059
10	85.67	63.67	29.91	280.6	208.5	104.2	0.196	0.036
Average	78.30	63.85	23.20	254.8	207.7	80.9	0.484	0.052
St. Dev.	5.31	1.10	4.97	18.5	3.5	17.3	0.405	0.018

D_{11} and D_{66} have a less effect on the deflection for the case studied here. Hence, large deviations in D_{11} and D_{66} do not cause large deviations in deflection values, and it is difficult to determine them from the displacement measurements used here. EMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEThe loading used in the second experiment is symmetric; as a result, the shear force effects are much lower compared to the other experiments. Any D_{66} value that is far away from the expected values adds very little contribution to the deflection value. In the second experiment, the average difference per node is 0.065 mm although the D_{66} value is far away from the expected value. Note that the D_{66} value of the second experiment is not used in the calculation of average D_{66} .

EMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDEMBEDETo check the sensitivity of the results, the 26 nodal displacements on the edge $y = 250$ mm are tabulated when one of the four material properties E_x , E_y , G_{xy} and ν_{xy} is changed to 80 to 120 percent of its original value keeping the other three material properties constant. The results tabulated in Tables 7-9 show that approximately a 10 percent increase in E_y results in a 10 percent decrease in deflections. Whereas a 10 percent increase in ν_{xy} and E_x results in approximately 1 percent change in deflection values. A 10 percent increase in G_{xy} results in a 1 percent increase in deflection in the first experiment, about 0.07 percent decrease in the second experiment, and approximately 5 percent decrease in the third experiment (See Table 5 for loading information). The change in G_{xy} varies because torsion induced by the loading is different for the three casesEMBED. To have an idea on the amount of twist induced, the minimum and maximum displacement values on the edge $y=250$ mm can be checked: in the first experiment, they are 5.94 mm and 9.82 mm, in the second experiment 7.83 mm and 8.33 mm, and in the third experiment 0.76 mm and 10.51 mm respectively. As it is seen, the minimum twist is induced in the second experiment, and the largest twist is induced in the third experiment.

E_x and E_y obtained from standard tensile test results, and the results obtained using the proposed inverse method are very close (Tables 4 and 6). The dominant elastic modulus E_y is found to vary with a lower standard deviation than the tensile test results. The average value of G_{xy} is as expected compared to shear modulus values found in literature for that kind of sheet metals. Deflections calculated by using different combinations of the three elastic moduli yield very close results to the exact deflection values once the dominant elastic modulus is calculated correctly. If the elastic moduli identified by the proposed study are to be used for different geometry, boundary conditions and

